

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
1. The chatbot looks and sounds friendly	<input type="radio"/>				
2. It was easy to find the functions I was looking for	<input type="radio"/>				
3. I did not find the text and button modes comfortable to use	<input type="radio"/>				
4. The chatbot explained its scope and purpose very well	<input type="radio"/>				
5. The chatbot did not cope well with any errors or mistakes	<input type="radio"/>				
6. I learn much new knowledge about marine species	<input type="radio"/>				
7. The chatbot instructions were hard to understand	<input type="radio"/>				

8. The chatbot's statistical feedback was helpful

9. I did not find the learning experience with chatbot engaging

10. The chatbot may sustain my participation in the Koster's project

11. I am satisfied with the chatbot performance

12. The chatbot presence can make me a long-term volunteer